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Shaping the Future of European Manufacturing as a Service

Five sister projects enabling on-demand, secure and sustainable MaaS for Europe.

The goal of these projects is to drive European manufacturing towards flexible, decentralised, and sustainable production. Through AI, trusted data spaces, digital twins, and advanced manufacturing, they will empower industries of all sizes to innovate, collaborate, and reduce environmental impact.

Funded by
the European Union

MaaS AI

Agile manufacturing made smart

MaaS AI is building an AI-driven platform that automates supplier–manufacturer interactions in a Manufacturing as a Service ecosystem. By enabling agile, transparent negotiations and on-demand sustainable production, it lowers SME entry barriers, optimises resources, and supports the shift to circular manufacturing.

Pilot domains: Cross-sector pilots

Lasers4MaaS

High-tech lasers, greener factories

Lasers4MaaS uses advanced laser technology and AI to deliver fast, flexible, and eco-friendly manufacturing. Its platform enables on-demand production without costly equipment changes, reduces waste and energy use, and brings high-tech laser capabilities to industries from automotive to food.

Pilot domains: Automotive, Aerospace, Energy, Pharma, Food.

MEDUSA

Democratising manufacturing services in Europe

MEDUSA is creating a secure, trusted framework for data exchange, asset servitisation, and AI services compliant with the EU AI Act. By connecting marketplaces across sectors, it aims to democratise access to advanced manufacturing services for businesses of all sizes in Europe.

Pilot domains: Mechanical parts, Electronic components

UniMaaS

Connecting manufacturing resources like never before

UniMaaS is developing a unified platform with suites for data modelling, resource modelling, and decision-making, enhancing access to customized manufacturing services. Using Digital Twins, Data Spaces, and AI optimisation, UniMaaS will offer flexible, decentralised manufacturing services, streamlining manufacturing processes, reducing costs, and promoting sustainability across sectors.

Pilot domains: Aircraft maintenance, Automotive seating, 3D construction printing, Logistics/warehouse management

REED

Reimagining large, bulky parts

REED is building a MaaS platform to revolutionise the production of large, complex parts in the capital goods industry . It creates flexible, collaborative value networks that boost productivity, ensure precision, and reduce environmental impact.

Pilot domains: Yellow Goods, Metal Forming & Metal Cutting Machinery